

FROM SELF TO STYLE: A STUDY OF BRAND LOYALTY AND SELF-ESTEEM AS CATALYSTS FOR FASHION CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

This study endeavors to analyze brand loyalty and investigate the impact of factors such as self-esteem and fashion consciousness on it, as it is imperative for organizations to comprehend consumer behavior and purchasing decisions. Data was collected from 400 participants using the purposive sampling technique. The descriptive statistics were used to determine the effectiveness of the scales, the frequency of occurrences, and the percentages. We also employed correlation analysis to investigate the direct and inverse effects of changes in one variable on changes in another. Furthermore, regression analysis demonstrated that self-esteem and fashion consciousness were substantially correlated with brand loyalty, and a T-test analysis was conducted with respect to gender, marital status, and occupation. There were statistically significant gender differences in brand loyalty and fashion consciousness. Measures of self-esteem and brand loyalty yielded significantly higher scores for married individuals than for unmarried individuals. This investigation determined that self-esteem was the sole category in which the mean ratings of employed and jobless participants differed substantially. This study explores self-esteem, a frequently disregarded aspect of consumer psychology, by examining fashion consciousness, measuring brand loyalty among adult consumers in the given context, and identifying fashion information sources.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary business environment, brand loyalty should be adopted as a fundamental principle across all sectors, particularly in light of increasing customer demands and environmental issues. This convergence is most apparent in the fashion industry, which has been frequently criticized for its resource-intensive practices and rapid trend cycles. Recent study on consumer behavior highlights the increasing significance of sustainable brand selection, influenced by characteristics such as self-esteem and fashion awareness (Cervellon & Wernerfelt, 2021; Park & Lin, 2020). As global consumers grow more cognizant

of environmental and ethical concerns, marketing techniques and consumer psychology must adapt to align with these changing ideals. In this setting, green marketing, which emphasizes environmentally friendly products, has emerged as a crucial strategy for brand differentiation and fostering enduring customer loyalty (Kong et al., 2022).

There is a lack of empirical research in developing economies about the relationship between self-Esteem and fashion consciousness, in contrast to studies conducted in Western markets. For example, Tran et al. (2022) highlighted the fashion consciousness among

Generation Z in industrialized nations, but they urged more confirmation on a regional level, particularly in South Asia. To fill this need, this study looks at the Pakistani setting, an expanding market with a growing youth population and a lot of people interested in digital fashion (Ahmed et al., 2023), to see how self-esteem, fashion awareness, and brand loyalty all play a role.

The growth of e-commerce, influencer marketing, and localized branding techniques have brought about a major transition in Pakistan's fashion business, which was previously defined by informal commerce and traditional retail (Khan & Rehman, 2022). Consumers' ability to express themselves, their sense of aesthetic harmony, and their social standing increasingly influence the relationship between companies (both established and emerging) and their target audiences. Brand loyalty and sustainability-oriented purchasing are impacted by psychological constructs including self-esteem and fashion consciousness, which constitute the foundation of this change (Lee et al., 2023).

Based on theories of self-expansion, self-congruity, and identity signaling, this study employs a theoretical framework. According to these models, brand loyalty isn't just about making a sale; it develops when customers' sense of identity aligns with the symbolic meanings associated with brands (Sirgy, 1982; Japutra et al., 2014). Brand loyalty may help make up for low self-esteem in collectivist cultures like Pakistan, where societal standards play a significant role in shaping individual actions (Santos et al., 2022). The impact of these constructs on brand loyalty across gender, marital status, and occupation is investigated in this study, which focuses on the Pakistani textile market.

Literature Review

Individuals' attire may represent their cultural views and values. The attire conveys significant information about your identity. The customer sense of style, confidence, and even its absence are significant and should be understood in relation to other factors (Sadatmoosavi et al., 2016). The reason behind this is that researchers dedicate a lot of time and energy to analyzing the characteristics of clothes purchasers, which contributes to the industry's growth and success. With constant style shifts and ever-shifting consumer tastes, the clothing industry makes it even

more challenging to know what to buy. There is a lack of research into the psychology of clothing consumption, despite the abundance of data available to garment marketers regarding the demographics of various segments of the apparel consumer base (Goldsmith et al., 2012). Below, we've included a couple of studies that help to define self-esteem, fashion consciousness, and brand loyalty and how they relate to certain demographic variables.

Fashion consciousness expresses the level of connection with style or fashion. What makes them unique is their impeccable taste in apparel and how they present themselves (Gam et al., 2007). Customers that care a great deal about staying current with fashion rely heavily on mass media for this information (Nam, 2006). People become more conscious of fashion due to the comparisons that occur in the media. This is because advertisements featuring models and celebrities encourage viewers to evaluate their own attractiveness in relation to these ideals (Lee & Workman, 2011).

People who care about fashion tend to spend more money on clothing because they see it as a reflection of who they are (Anand & Kaur, 2018). They care more about clothing, shop more frequently, and donate more money to charity than those who aren't fashion-savvy (Kim et al., 2018). Consumers can be price-sensitive and limited by their financial goals, which in turn reduces shopping time; nonetheless, few studies show that purchasing is not primarily driven by fashion consciousness. Despite this, people may have a positive attitude toward shopping and continue to buy clothes to update their wardrobes and improve their looks (Iyer et al., 2010; Walsh et al., 2001). Future research with more variables is required to examine the impact of fashion consciousness on outcome factors. This was part of an experimental study that looked at how people's consumption of clothing altered during the epidemic. This study aimed to understand how people reacted to buying clothes during the global COVID-19 pandemic by incorporating perspectives on handling stress and adjusting to new situations. Liu et al. (2021) found that one of the main ways to manage stress is by making changes to one's consuming habits.

Brand loyalty. When consumers are loyal to a brand, they are more likely to continue buying that brand or one with similar characteristics, even when faced with opportunities presented by competing products or services or by persuasive advertising (Ali, 2019). Thus, it can be viewed as the actions taken by a customer following the purchase or their commitment to continue purchasing from the same company. According to Tran et al. (2015), brands often portray firms that rely on spouse permission as having a more cohabitative image. Even in a stagnant market, many brands aspire to be seen as adapting and expanding in novel ways (Nguyen et al., 2015). When consumers identify with a particular brand, they are more likely to buy that brand's products rather than those of rival companies. As a result, consumers become loyal to the brand. A company's greatest asset is its strong brand. In the process of gaining and maintaining customers' loyalty, they aid the firm in its battle for a larger portion of the market. Nowadays, brands play a significant role in Pakistani society. Because they are materialistic, young people are more likely to be loyal customers and brand advocates. Like in Pakistan, the garment industry has seen tremendous growth in recent years, thanks in large part to the globalization of trade. When deciding which brand to purchase, consumers take many factors into account. A brand-conscious customer, according to the research of Jin et al. (2009), chooses a brand to express their identity, social status, and consumer confidence while also satisfying their need for novelty. When making a purchase, buyers factor in their level of familiarity with the brand. Brands that resonate with consumers' values and sense of self tend to do better in the marketplace (Chaplin & John, 2005). According to Japutra (2014) and Macinnis et al. (2008), the most important factor in determining an emotional commitment to a brand is the impression of self-consistency. According to Coelho and Ferreira (2015) and Hudson et al. (2015), item contribution is a crucial factor that affects the consumer-brand relationship and the trustworthiness of the brand. Building brand loyalty is challenging, but in the last several decades, it has risen to the status of a top marketing priority due to increased competition. Customers who are truly loyal do more than just make repeat purchases; they also spread the word about how great your business is and stand behind you when you

confront uncooperative companies. In a 2009 study, Raju et al. That group, the Dossemet al. (2013) found that brand devoted consumers go the extra mile—as long as they stay loyal and become brand advocates. As Soomro and Issani (2017) pointed out, brand customers in the later stages become the ones spreading the word about the company's brand. There is a dearth of studies examining the factors that influence developing-world consumers' propensity to remain loyal to certain brands (Das, 2016). Vietnam and Turkey are among the developed nations where most studies on the relationship between brand responsiveness, brand image, trust, engagement, and loyalty have been conducted (Erkmen & Hancer, 2019; Sock, 2018; Tran et al., 2019).

Self-Esteem is how much a person thinks they are worth or how much they value themselves. The Oxford Dictionary says it implies "trusting in your own worth or abilities." It reveals how much people value and like themselves, which can change how they feel, act, and are motivated. In a worldwide business environment where production and manufacturing companies are in severe competition, rising crises and a lack of resources continue to threaten economic stability. This has made the job of policymakers much harder and made tensions between economies even worse. Corporate social responsibility has become much more important during global disruptions like pandemics. In this unstable environment, businesses need to focus on customer-focused traits like brand loyalty, patronage, and trust, as well as psychological factors like self-esteem, which affect how people act and what they want to buy. Millennials are more conscious of crises connected to sustainability, ethical consumption, and socially responsible practices than any other generation, according to research in developed countries (Tran et al., 2022). These dynamics underscore the necessity for additional research in developing economies to investigate the elements that foster brand loyalty, especially in scenarios where sustainable consumption promotes ethical involvement and the elevation of human self-esteem. Research conducted in Pakistan corresponds with these investigative priorities. The primary objective of this research is to ascertain the factors that drive consumers to exceed expectations in their quest for brand loyalty, frequently as a manifestation of identity and social

affiliation. According to self-expansion theory, the symbolic and functional correlation in consumer decisions functions as a mechanism for social conformity and self-enhancement, reflecting fundamental psychological requirements such as self-worth and identity affirmation. Consequently, the current study establishes a theoretical framework based on self-expansion theory to investigate these relationships. It aims to analyze the relationship among self-esteem, fashion awareness, and brand loyalty, especially on the gender disparity in fashion. This poll covers a wide range of Pakistani clothing companies. The increasing brand and fashion awareness, materialistic tendencies, and consumer loyalty among the youth highlight the significance of this study and its capacity to elucidate the impact of self-esteem on customer attachment within fashion markets.

Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional survey methodology to examine correlations between psychological constructs. A total of 400 adult participants, including 199 men and 201 women, were chosen through convenience sampling. The data was gathered from cities such as Rawalpindi and Islamabad in Pakistan, which were assumed to have both brand outliers and brand conscious buyers. People between the ages of 18 and 65 who claimed to have bought clothes from well-known brands were considered for the study.

Three standardized psychological measures, including the State Self-Esteem Scale (Heatherton & Polivy, 1991), the Fashion Consciousness Scale (Gould & Stern, 1988), and the Brand Loyalty Scale (Rundle-Thiele, 2005), along with an informed consent form and a demographic data sheet, made up the instrument. Clarity was ensured by translating and pilot testing all instruments into Urdu. Scales demonstrated high levels of internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha scores ranging from .84 to .91.

Higher scores indicated more levels of the concept in question, and participants used Likert-type scales to reply to the items. We used SPSS (v.26) to analyze the data, which included t-tests, correlation, multiple regression, and descriptive statistics to see whether there were any differences by gender, marital status, or profession. In the Pakistani twin cities, participants

were solicited as buyers of various apparel brands. We contacted each person separately. Initially, 450 participants were contacted; however, data from 50 of them were excluded since their information was inadequate. Participants have to be adults (18–65 years old) in order to be considered. Informed consent, a demographic sheet, and five more scales were part of the questionnaires that participants were given in order to gather data. The participants were informed about the study's objectives and methodology. We told them that their information would be handled with the utmost confidentiality and utilized exclusively for research. If they did not want to continue, they might withdraw at any moment; that was communicated to them. The goal was to get them to choose the answer that most reflected their opinions. The analysis was conducted using the following scales.

State Self Esteem Scale

Based on the popular Janis-Field Feelings of Inadequacy Scale (Janis & Field, 1959), Heatherton and Polivy (1991) developed the 20-item State Self-Esteem Scale (SSES). Appropriateness, social standing, and performance are the three domains of self-esteem that the SSES assesses. Using it, one may better manage manipulation, measure clinical changes, and find hidden connections. The reliability coefficient for the scale is 0.88, and the alpha coefficients for social, performance, and beauty self-esteem are all positive.

Fashion Consciousness Scale

Gould and Stern (1988), were the ones who came up with the style consciousness scale. It uses a five-point Likert scale, from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," to assess 31 topics pertaining to fashion consciousness (1–5). Using a five-point Likert scale, the 31 items that make up the Fashion Consciousness Scale were created by Gould and Stern in 1988. It gauges how self-conscious people generally are and how they generally perceive fashion consciousness. With a score range of 31–155 and a reliability of 0.96, it is translated into Urdu.

Brand Loyalty Scale

Rundle (2004) created the Brand Loyalty Scale to assess five sides of consumer devotion: attitude, complaint behavior, tendency to remain loyal,

resistance to competing offers, and situational loyalty. It is essential for marketers to establish retention metrics with a reliability range of 0.70 to 0.83.

Data Analyses

Table 1

Psychometric properties of scales (N=400)

Scales	N	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Actual	Potential		
SES	20	57.90	24.85	.84	28-96	20-100	.345	-.434
PSE	7	20.29	5.29	.69	9-30	7-35	.477	-.520
SSE	7	20.33	5.98	.74	11-28	7-35	.386	-.529
ASE	6	18.42	4.24	.57	8-27	6-30	.250	-.348
FCS	31	90.25	27.19	.89	31-147	31-155	-.094	-.052
BLS	26	45.20	8.81	.92	26-117	26-182	.562	.946
AL	6	21.32	8.72	.86	8-31	6-30	.113	-.680
CB	7	23.42	8.98	.81	9-32	7-35	.092	-.428
PTL	4	15.42	5.71	.68	6-18	4-20	.060	-.456
RCO	6	22.21	7.71	.81	7-27	6-30	-.140	-.299
SL	3	11.31	4.81	.81	5-12	3-15	.084	-.426

Note: The acronyms SE, PSE, SSE, ASE, FC, BL, AL, CB, PTL, RCO, and SL stand for various concepts related to self-esteem, performance, attitude, appearance, fashion consciousness, propensity to be loyal, resistance to competing offers, and situational

loyalty. The reliability, validity, and validity of the Self-Esteem, Fashion Consciousness, and Brand Loyalty scales, as well as their respective subscales, are displayed in Table 1.

Table 2

Demographic details of participants (N=400)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	199	49.8
Female	201	50.3
Marital status		
Unmarried	249	62.3
Married	151	37.8
Occupation		
Unemployed	222	55.5
Employed	177	44.3

The demographic information of the participants is displayed in Table 2 using percentages and frequencies. The participants were requested to provide details regarding their gender, marital status,

and profession. The twin cities of Pakistan were the sites of the data collection. A greater proportion of females took part. Respondents who were not

married nor employed made up a larger proportion of the total.

Figure: Correlation Matrix

Table 3
Correlation between Self-Esteem Scale, Fashion Consciousness Scale and Brand Loyalty Scale along with their subscales (N=400)

Scales	SE	PSE	SSE	ASE	FCS	BL	AL	CB	PTL	RCO	SL
SE		.91**	.90**	.84**	.32**	-.11**	-.06	.10**	-.04	.16**	.11**
PSE			.72**	.66**	.16**	-.06	-.01	-.07	-.01	-.12**	-.07
SSE				.59**	.00	.15**	-.04	-.10*	-.09	-.19**	-.15**
ASE					.21**	-.06	.03	.00	-.10*	-.04	.09
FCS						.46**	.36**	.27**	.40**	.38**	.39**
BL							.81**	.79**	.81**	.81**	-.69**
AL								.54	.51**	.50**	.49**
CB									.46**	.51**	.38*
PTL										.63**	.49**
RCO											.59
SL											

The table 3 indicates about how a person's self-esteem can be measure in several ways: performance self-esteem (PSE), social self-esteem (SSE), and appearance self-esteem (ASE). Fashionista = aware of current trends Situational loyalty (SL), propensity to be loyal (PTL), resistance to competing offers (RTCO), and attitude loyalty (BL) are the variables that make up brand loyalty (BL), attitude loyalty (AL), complaint behavior (CB), and so on. The relationships between the self-esteem, fashion consciousness, and brand loyalty scores and subscales are displayed in Table 3. The results show that there is a negative correlation between self-esteem and brand loyalty. This implies that an individual's brand loyalty decreases as their self-esteem increases, and the reverse is also true. There is a strong positive correlation between fashion consciousness and brand loyalty. This correlation demonstrates that brand loyalty rises in tandem with fashion consciousness and falls in the opposite direction.

Table 4

This study used a multiple regression model with 400 participants to examine the relationship between self-esteem, fashion consciousness, and brand loyalty.

Brand Loyalty V-A	B	SE	β	t	P	95%CI	
						LL	UL
Self-Esteem	.32	.09	-.16	-3.9	.00	-.52	-.17
Fashion consciousness	.68	.06	.48	10.9	.00	.56	.81

R²=.245, ΔR²=.24, F=64.5*

A class interval, a lower limit, a level of significance, a standardized beta, a standard error, a t test statistic, a standardized beta, a standardized beta, a p-value, and a class interval The outcome variable (brand loyalty) was explained by the predictors to a degree of 24%

(R²=.24, F= 43.3), as shown in table 4. Brand loyalty was favorably predicted by self-esteem and fashion consciousness, but by materialism, the effect was non-significant.

Table 5

Disparities between the sexes on measures of self-esteem, fashion awareness, and brand loyalty (N = 400)

Variables	Male (n=199)		Female (n=201)		t	P	95%CL		Cohen's D
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
SE	60.03	14.5	59.08	14.8	-.01	.98	-2.8	-2.7	-
PSE	20.44	5.15	21.15	6.41	.57	.68	-.78	1.4	-
SSE	20.43	5.94	20.13	5.97	-.49	.64	-.89	1.9	-
ASE	19.21	5.27	19.72	4.29	-1.5	.16	-1.5	.23	-
FC	87.66	18.95	91.92	19.5	-3.4	.01	-9.8	-2.9	0.32
BL	88.43	28.7	97.03	28.1	-2.9	.01	-13.8	-2.3	0.29
AL	19.87	8.72	21.70	8.63	-2.4	.03	-1.8	-.02	0.18
CB	22.83	8.37	24.00	9.88	-.34	.90	-2.2	1.7	-
PTL	14.34	5.67	15.61	6.59	-3.8	.01	-3.6	-1.4	0.40
RCO	22.13	7.89	22.19	8.33	-2.4	.01	-3.4	-5.7	0.35
SL	13.09	4.31	11.52	6.14	-3.6	.01	-2.1	-2.2	0.32

NOTE: ASE stands for Appearance Self-Esteemedness, PSE for Performance Self-Esteemedness, and SES for Social Self-Esteemedness. A measure of how much people care about fashion, the FCS ranks Named after the Brand Loyalty Scale, The acronyms AL, CB, PTL, RCO, and SL stand for "attitudinal loyalty," "propensity to be loyal," "resistance to competing offers," and "situational

loyalty," respectively. Mean differences among genders are seen in Table 5. There are statistically significant differences between all of the variables except self-esteem, according to the results. On the whole, women did better than men on every single measure, with the exception of self-esteem, which was unchanged.

Table 6

Disparities in self-esteem, fashion awareness, and brand loyalty among marital status groups (N = 400)

Variables	Unmarried (n=249)		Married (n=151)		t	P	95%CL		Cohen's D
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	

SE	60.24	13.1	57.08	14.4	2.2	.02	.39	5.9	0.22
PSE	20.73	5.11	19.55	5.51	2.1	.03	.11	2.2	0.22
SSE	20.85	6.11	19.47	5.68	2.2	.02	.17	2.5	.067
ASE	18.64	4.13	18.05	4.39	1.3	.17	.17	2.5	-
FC	88.99	20.1	88.41	17.6	.29	.76	-3.3	4.4	-
BL	92.03	25.1	87.31	30.0	1.68	.05	-.78	10.2	0.17
AL	21.5	7.78	19.7	9.62	2.08	.03	.10	3.5	0.22
CB	23.4	8.37	22.2	9.37	1.37	.16	-.53	3.0	-
PTL	14.5	5.62	14.2	5.73	.42	.67	-.90	1.3	-
RCO	21.5	7.36	20.4	7.92	1.36	.17	-.47	2.6	-
SL	10.9	4.69	10.6	4.93	.66	.05	-.64	1.3	0.06

NOTE: ASE stands for Appearance Self-Esteemedness, PSE for Performance Self-Esteemedness, and SES for Social Self-Esteemedness. A measure of how much people care about fashion, the FCS ranks Named after the Brand Loyalty Scale, Affective Devotion SL stands for "situational loyalty," "RCO" for "resistance to competing offers," "PTL" for "propensity to be loyal," and "CB" for "complaining

behavior." The results of the comparison between the married and single participants are displayed in Table 6. Mean scores of fashion consciousness are not statistically significant, but there are substantial disparities in levels of self-esteem and brand loyalty. People who aren't married tend to have strong opinions about themselves and their favorite brands.

Table 7
Variations in self-esteem, fashion awareness, and brand loyalty among occupations (N = 400)

Variables	Unemployed (n=223)		Employed (n=177)		t	p	95%CL		Cohen's D
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
SE	62.04	14.0	58.56	15.1	3.3	.01	1.8	7.2	0.33
PSE	20.9	4.98	19.42	5.5	2.9	.03	.25	2.6	0.22
SSE	21.22	5.83	19.18	5.9	3.5	.00	.93	3.2	0.34
ASE	18.76	4.29	17.96	4.1	1.8	.01	1.7	7.1	-
FC	89.79	19.5	87.60	81.8	1.1	.29	.52	2.6	-
BL	91.34	24.9	89.09	29.7	.28	.41	-.65	2.5	-
AL	13.36	5.64	13.23	5.7	.44	.65	-.77	2.0	-
CB	24.75	8.5	23.09	9.3	2.8	.06	-1.4	1.1	-
PTL	15.41	5.8	55.51	5.8	.19	.89	-.08	2.2	-
RCO	22.40	11.7	22.87	7.9	.67	.49	-1.2	.33	-
SL	12.72	4.5	12.94	4.9	.48	.67	-.97	.75	-

NOTE: A measure of one's sense of self-worth, SES This stands for "Assessment of Social Impressions," "Performance Self-Esteemed," and "Social Self-Esteemed." A measure of how much people care about fashion, the FCS ranks Named after the Brand Loyalty Scale, Affective Devotion Propensity to Be Loyal (PTL) and Complaining Behavior (CB) "RCO" stands for "Resistance to Competing Offers," Loyalty

in specific contexts Distinctions between the employed and the jobless are displayed in Table 7. While there is no statistically significant difference in levels of brand loyalty between the employed and the unemployed, there is a substantial difference in self-esteem. In addition, the majority of the unemployed participants who had high scores across the board

were female, which likely contributed to their overall high scores relative to the working participants.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis showed that there was a balanced representation of genders and employment statuses, with a little increase in the number of respondents who were neither married nor employed. All subscales were found to have appropriate psychometric qualities according to reliability analyses.

Correlation Analysis:

People who had higher levels of self-esteem were less inclined to show strong commitment to a particular brand, as indicated by the negative correlation between self-esteem and brand loyalty ($r = -0.11$, $p < .01$). The data suggests that being aware of trends is associated with both internal psychological qualities and brand attachment, as fashion consciousness was found to be positively correlated with both self-esteem ($r = 0.23$, $p < .01$) and brand loyalty ($r = 0.46$, $p < .01$).

Regression Analysis: Brand loyalty was found to be adversely correlated with self-esteem ($\beta = -0.16$, $p < .001$), according to a multiple regression analysis. Customer loyalty to a brand was positively correlated with fashion consciousness ($\beta = 0.48$, $p < .001$). According to the statistical analysis, these factors explained 24% of the variation in brand loyalty ($R^2 = .24$, $F = 64.5$, $p < .001$).

T-Test Analyses:

Gender: Although there was no significant difference in self-esteem, women reported far greater degrees of fashion consciousness and brand loyalty.

Marital Status: Consistent with previous research indicating stronger brand connection among younger, single consumers, the percentage of unmarried people scored considerably higher on measures of self-esteem and brand loyalty.

Employment Status: There may be distinct societal pressures or ways of constructing identity in non-working populations, since the unemployed participants (most of whom were women) scored higher on self-esteem.

Ethical sourcing claims, green marketing language, and sustainability certifications are becoming more popular, according to exploratory post hoc research, which expanded upon the main analysis's focus on psychological determinants. This is in line with broader trends that demonstrate that urban consumers in Pakistan, especially Gen Z, are becoming more receptive to messages about the environment and brands being transparent about their practices (Ahmed et al., 2023; Kong et al., 2022). Both individual psychological characteristics and marketing methods based on ethical and environmental positioning impact fashion brand loyalty, according to these data. This study delves at the relationship between consumer confidence and fashion awareness as it pertains to clothing brand loyalty. The subscales and the entire set of measures all exhibit high levels of alpha reliability. In this study, only noteworthy outcomes are covered. There is a positive and statistically significant relationship between self-esteem and fashion consciousness, according to the correlation study. Relatedly, prior research has shown that style-conscious consumers will gladly shell out more cash for apparel since they see it as a reflection of their individuality (Kaur & Anand, 2018). They shop more frequently, spend more money, and are more drawn to clothing items than people who are less fashion-conscious (Kim et al., 2018).

Brand loyalty is negatively correlated with self-esteem. Researchers wanted to see if there was a correlation between the need to show off one's social position and boost one's self-esteem and the frequency with which people bought branded fashion items. A favorable and direct relationship between consumption and social status display was found in the results of the questionnaire survey that was done. According to studies, one's social standing significantly affects their sense of self-worth, suggesting an inverse association between social standing and materialistic purchasing. Further, the findings indicate that individuals with lower self-esteem are more likely to engage in materialistic consumption (M'Saad et al., 2011).

There is a strong positive relationship between fashion consciousness and brand loyalty. People who care about their social standing often purchase expensive clothing in the fashion industry. Customers that care about fashion are likely to think

about how the item will make them seem when making a purchase. They would become more materialistic as a result of their desire to acquire more expensive goods (Leung et al., 2015). O'Cass (2004) conducted research on brand loyalty and fashion consciousness, and the results showed that both materialists and fashion-conscious people value having prestigious branded things more.

Brand loyalty is significantly predicted by self-esteem and fashion consciousness, according to regression research. Consumers who rate themselves highly are more likely to remain loyal to the brands they love (Malar et al., 2011). According to another research, customers' level of fashion consciousness is a significant factor that could influence their emotional connection, happiness, and loyalty to a brand as a result of their participation in the product development process. According to Michaelaelidou and Dibb (2009), brand loyalty is more prevalent among customers that are fashion conscious.

Mean ratings on fashion consciousness and brand loyalty were significantly different, according to T-test analysis. On the other hand, women were more concerned with style than men were with brand loyalty. Women care more about their looks and sense of self than men do, and they are more invested in the fashion industry as a whole. Fashion apparel is a means of self-definition and self-identification for women, who often give garments symbolic meaning. Many believe that the "feminine" symbolism in clothing explains why women are so drawn to the fashion industry. According to research by Khare and Rakesh, there is a gender gap in how much time Indian teenagers spend interacting with ads for trendy apparel. There appears to be a gender gap in how men and women feel about participating in the fashion industry. The way people live now has a major impact on what they buy (Khare et al., 2012).

The findings reinforce the significance of consumers' active engagement with the brand, their perception of its quality, and their passion for the brand as foundational factors in the relationship between brand gender and brand loyalty. As a result, this study adds to what is already known about brand gender and backs up the value of a distinct gender positioning for brands by demonstrating how strong gender identity increases brand loyalty (Carvalho et al., 2020). The results showed that self-esteem and brand loyalty

were significantly different on average depending on marital status. In addition, compared to married people, single people scored much higher. Significant differences in occupational status were also found, as were variances in self-esteem mean scores. People who do not work tend to have better self-esteem than those who do.

Conclusion

By clarifying the relationship between fashion consciousness and brand loyalty in an emerging market environment, this study adds to the literature on sustainable consumer behavior. With the rise of values-based consumption in the post-pandemic era, consumers' expectations have evolved, and the use of green marketing cues as a backdrop reflects this.

This research has important practical implications for Pakistani fashion companies, who must develop strategies that cater to consumers' symbolic and aesthetic desires while simultaneously establishing sustainability as an essential part of their brand identity. In order to build trust in their brands, especially among younger, more trend-conscious consumers, marketers should highlight honesty and moral messaging.

To get to the heart of what consumers are saying, future studies should look at longitudinal designs and use qualitative metrics. It is possible that more generalizable conclusions may be obtained if the focus was expanded beyond metropolitan centers. In order to create meaningful relationships between brands and consumers in different cultural contexts, it is crucial to understand the psychosocial drivers of loyalty, especially as sustainability becomes an increasingly important factor in global brand strategy.

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